

**AUTOMATED COCONUT SHELL CHARCOAL POWDER
MAKING MACHINE**

PROJECT REPORT

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*in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the award of the degree*

of

BACHELOR OF ENGINEERING

IN

MECHATRONICS ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF MECHATRONICS ENGINEERING

KONGU ENGINEERING COLLEGE

(Autonomous)

PERUNDURAI ERODE – 638 060

NOVEMBER 2023

DEPARTMENT OF MECHATRONICS ENGINEERING

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NOVEMBER 2023

BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

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We affirm that the Project Report titled **AUTOMATED COCONUT SHELL CHARCOAL POWDER MAKING MACHINE**, being submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Engineering is the original work carried out by us. It has not formed the part of any other project report or dissertation on the basis of which a degree or award was conferred on an earlier occasion on this or any other candidate.

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ABSTRACT

This project report presents the design and development of an automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine. Coconut shell charcoal is a widely used material in various industries, including agriculture, medicine, and cosmetics. However, the traditional methods of producing charcoal powder from coconut shells are labor-intensive and time-consuming. The objective of this project is to create an automated machine that could efficiently convert coconut shells into high-quality charcoal powder. The machine employs a series of mechanical processes, including shredding, carbonizing, crushing, and screening to produce fine charcoal powder.

The design process involved careful consideration of the functional requirements, safety measures, and operational efficiency. The machine consists of several components, including a shredder, furnace, two in one twin shaft crusher & screener and a control system. Each component is designed and integrated to ensure smooth operation and minimal manual intervention. The crusher is responsible for breaking down the burned coconut shells into smaller fragments, while the screener helps to filter and eliminates the larger particles, ensuring proper combustion during the carbonization process. The grinder reduces the dried shells into a fine powder suitable for various applications. The control system automates the operation, allowing for precise control of the machine's parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, our sincere thanks to the almighty, who has blessed us to accomplish the project successfully. Then we thanked our correspondent, **Thiru. A. K. ILANGO, B.Com., MBA., LLB** and all the members of Kongu Vellalar Institute of Technology Trust for providing us with a plethora facility to complete our project in a successful manner.

We wish to express our sincere thanks to our beloved Principal **Dr. V. BALUSAMY B.E., (Hons) M. Tech., Ph.D.**, for allowing us to have the extensive use of college facilities to do this project. We solemnly express our gratitude to our Head of the Department **Dr. S. SHANKAR M.E., Ph.D.**, for his guidance, support, and encouragement.

We take immense pleasure to express our heartfelt thanks to our beloved project supervisor **Dr. R. PARAMESHWARAN M.E., Ph.D.**, for his valuable suggestions, guidance and constant support provided all through the course of the project.

We also thank our project coordinators **Dr. K. GOMATHI M.E., Ph.D.**, and **Mr. P. M. ARUNKUMAR M.E.**, for their invaluable mentoring support provided throughout the project duration.

We express our sincere thanks to all teaching and non-teaching staff members of Mechatronics Engineering Department. We also extend our warm thanks to our beloved parents and friends.

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LIST OF UNITS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Alternate Current
cm	Centimeter
DC	Direct current
HP	Horsepower
Kg	Kilogram
mm	Millimeter
N	Newton
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
rpm	Revolution per minute
Pa	Pascal
V	Voltage
C	Celsius
PSI	Pounds per square inch
Hz	Hertz
L	Liter
A	Ampere
CFM	Cubic Feet per minute

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 CHARACTERISTICS OF COCONUT SHELL

Coconut shells exhibit exceptional hardness, providing them with a strong and durable outer shell. Despite their hardness, coconut shells are relatively lightweight, making them suitable for various applications where weight is a concern. The inner structure of coconut shells features a fibrous material called coir. This natural fiber, found between the hard shell and the outer husk, has multiple applications on its own. Coconut shells possess small pores that contribute to their porosity. This characteristic allows for air and water circulation, making them useful in filtration systems and as a growth medium for plants.

Coconut shells naturally resist decay and fungal growth, ensuring their longevity and durability over time. Coconut shells contain a significant amount of carbon, making them a valuable source of activated carbon. This activated carbon finds applications in water filtration, air purification, and various industrial processes. Due to their dense structure, coconut shells offer thermal insulation properties. Consequently, they can be utilized in the manufacturing of insulation boards and panels. As a by-product of the coconut industry, coconut shells contribute to waste reduction and the utilization of renewable resources, making them an environmentally friendly option. The natural texture and appearance of coconut shells make them visually appealing. They are often used in crafts, jewelry, and home decor to enhance aesthetic value. These characteristics collectively make coconut shells versatile and valuable in a wide range of applications.

1.2. CARBON POWDER EXTRACTION METHODS

1.2.1 Pyrolysis Method

Pyrolysis is a widely used method for extracting charcoal or carbon powder from organic materials, including coconut shells. The overview of the process is given below:

Preparation: The coconut shells are first cleaned and dried to remove any impurities or moisture.

Heating: The shells are then subjected to high temperatures in an oxygen-limited environment (such as a closed container or kiln). This process is called pyrolysis.

Cooling and Collection: After the pyrolysis process, the container is cooled, and the resulting charcoal is collected. It is then crushed or ground into a fine powder to obtain carbon powder.

1.2.2 Chemical Activation Method

Another method commonly used to extract activated carbon powder from coconut shells is chemical activation. This method involves the following steps:

Impregnation: The coconut shell charcoal is impregnated with a chemical activating agent such as phosphoric acid, zinc chloride, or potassium hydroxide. This agent helps create pores and increase the surface area of the resulting activated carbon.

Heat Treatment: The impregnated charcoal is then heated at a high temperature (typically between 500 to 900 degrees Celsius) in a controlled environment. This process activates the chemical agent and induces pore development within the charcoal structure.

Washing and Drying: The activated carbon is thoroughly washed to remove any residual chemicals or impurities. It is then dried to obtain activated carbon powder.

1.3 MOTIVATION OF PROJECT

The conventional methods of producing charcoal powder from coconut shells involve manual labor and extensive processing time. Hence it involves Manual shredding process is shown in Fig. 1.1 where the dried coconut shell is been shredded and converted into soft coconut fibers, this further carbonized in high flame where the workers must do their job in a smoky area is shown in Fig. 1.2 this might highly influence on causing air borne diseases and working on massive heat zone is shown in Fig. 1.3 may lead to heat stroke. The manual screening process is shown in Fig. 1.4 includes picking and crushing the burned shells.

The project's primary objective is to revolutionize the production of charcoal powder from coconut shells by introducing automation. Traditional methods involve arduous manual labor, leading to significant time consumption, exposure to smoke, and risk of heat-related health issues. By automating this process, the project seeks to alleviate the burden of labor-intensive tasks, promoting a healthier and safer work environment.

Charcoal powder obtained from coconut shells boasts versatile applications in

agriculture, medicine, cosmetics, and various industries. The escalating demand for high-quality charcoal powder necessitates a more efficient and consistent production approach. This is where the automated machine steps in, ensuring a steady supply of charcoal powder to meet the growing demand.

Fig. 1.1 Manual Shredding

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/eyDP8>)

Fig. 1.2 Labours on Smoky area

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/efoEU>)

Automation not only enhances production efficiency but also reduces operational costs, making it a sustainable and cost-effective solution. The automated machine outpaces manual methods, processing coconut shells at a considerably faster rate. Streamlining the production process is pivotal in enhancing cost-effectiveness for businesses and sustainable production of valuable charcoal powder.

Fig. 1.3 Labours on Heat zone

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/fnpx0>)

Fig. 1.4 Manual Screening

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/gqxz1>)

An automated machine for producing charcoal powder from coconut shells aims to replace labor-intensive and time-consuming manual methods, reducing health risks

to workers.

1.4. STRUCTURE OF THESIS

CHAPTER 1: In this chapter, the focus is on the rationale for creating the Automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine. It aims to improve the production process by addressing the limitations of existing systems.

CHAPTER 2: This chapter delves into a review of the literature concerning current systems related to the Automatic oil pumping machine. It also outlines the issues with the existing systems and introduces the proposed system.

CHAPTER 3: This section revolves around the feasibility analysis of the proposed system, encompassing economic, operational, and technical aspects.

CHAPTER 4: In this chapter, we provide an overview of the design, the components used for constructing the model, and the calculations made to evaluate the power requirements.

CHAPTER 5: This chapter discusses the Solidworks design of the entire system and explains how the fabricated setup works, offering insights into the mechanical and electrical components of the proposed system.

CHAPTER 6: This chapter summarizes the findings and potential future developments for the Automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine.

CHAPTER 7: This chapter is dedicated to the references used to inform the design and fabrication of the Automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Ahmad et al. (2021) conducted carbonization experiments of coconut shell biomass in a downdraft carbonization reactor to determine the effect of temperature on the charcoal properties. The study found that the higher the temperature, the better the charcoal quality, but the lower the charcoal yields. The coconut shell biomass was obtained from a local shop in Malaysia and heated in the reactor at a fixed residence time of 60 min and a particle size of 5 mm with nitrogen as a carrier gas. The study concluded that the carbonization reactor used in this study has the potential to produce an eco-friendly charcoal with superior quality properties that can assist in reducing environmental pollution, by proper selections of carbonization temperature

Ahmad et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive review of coconut shell powder composites, including their preparation, processing, and characterization. The study found that coconut shell powder is an interesting candidate for composites due to its chemical composition. The authors reviewed various studies on coconut shell powder composites and discussed the effects of different parameters on the properties of the composites. The review also highlighted the challenges and prospects of using coconut shell powder composites in various applications. Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the potential of coconut shell powder composites as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional composites

Arief et al. (2023) studied the coconut shell carbonization process using a smokeless kiln. The study found that traditional carbonization methods involving kilns can produce excessive smoke, polluting the environment and disrupting human activities. To address this issue, the authors fabricated a kiln made from a steel drum with a sealer belt to trap burning smoke inside the kiln. The results showed that adding this belt effectively reduced the smoke produced, making it more eco-friendly. The study also found that burning 25 kg of coconut shell was optimal, producing a 48% charcoal content. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using a smokeless kiln for coconut shell carbonization

Arena et al. (2016) conducted a life cycle assessment of activated carbon production from coconut shells. The study found that activated carbon produced from coconut shells has a clear environmental advantage over coal-based carbons. The authors evaluated the environmental impacts of the manufacturing chain of activated carbon produced from coconut shells in Indonesia, which is the major coconut producer country. The study used life cycle assessment and process analysis to quantify all the environmental interactions over the stages of the life cycle of an activated carbon manufacturing chain. The results showed that using electrical energy produced from renewable sources, such as biomass, would reduce the contributions to human toxicity (by up to 60%) and global warming (by up to 80%). The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using coconut shells as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional carbons

Anoop et al. (2011) studied the processing and utilization of coconut wood in Kerala. The study found that coconut wood can be used for various purposes, including furniture, handicrafts, and construction. The authors conducted a survey of coconut wood processing units in Kerala and found that the wood is primarily used for making furniture, followed by handicrafts and construction. The study also found that the wood has good mechanical properties, such as high strength and stiffness, making it suitable for structural applications. The authors recommended that more research be conducted to explore the potential of coconut wood as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional timbers

Baygan et al. (2016) studied coconut shell pyrolysis for optimum charcoal production. The study found that the optimal temperature for coconut shell pyrolysis is 400°C. The authors conducted experiments to determine the effect of temperature on the yield and quality of charcoal produced from coconut shells. The study found that the higher the temperature, the lower the yield of charcoal, but the better the quality. The study also found that the optimal particle size for coconut shells is 2-3 mm, and the optimal residence time is 60 minutes. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using coconut shells as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional charcoal

Bhatia et al. (2019) designed a multipurpose machine that can dehusk, cut, and grate coconuts. The machine has a toothed shaft containing spikes that dehusks the coconut,

followed by a cutting process that can punch the coconut if desired. Finally, the grated coconut is produced using a grating tool with notches on its periphery. The model would be beneficial for industries that use coconut as a raw material. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using a multipurpose machine to reduce the labor fatigue and injuries associated with manual dehusking, cutting, and grating of coconuts

Budi et al. (2016) produced activated coconut shell charcoal carbon using chemical-physical activation. The study found that the activated carbon produced has a high surface area and pore volume. The authors used a combination of chemical and physical activation methods to produce activated carbon from coconut shell charcoal. The study found that the optimal conditions for producing activated carbon were a temperature of 800°C, an activation time of 60 minutes, and a chemical-physical ratio of 1:1. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using coconut shell charcoal as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional activated carbon

Cobb and Clarkson (2012) developed a low-tech method for producing coconut shell activated charcoal. The study found that the method is simple, low-cost, and can be used to produce activated charcoal for various applications. The authors used a kiln made from a 55-gallon drum and a metal pipe to produce the charcoal. The study found that the optimal temperature for producing charcoal is between 400°C and 500°C. The study also found that the charcoal produced using this method has a high surface area and pore volume, making it suitable for various applications, such as water filtration and air purification

Dhamodaran et al. (1989) studied the calorific value variation in coconut stem wood. The study found that the average calorific value of coconut stem wood in air-dry condition was about 16.3 MJ/kg, which compares favorably with that of hardwoods. The study also found that there is a highly positive correlation between density and calorific value per unit volume, and a highly negative correlation between siliceous matter and calorific value. The authors recommended that the upper half of mature and over-mature palms and full length of young palms affected by root-wilt disease could be used as a fuelwood of adequate heating value or converted into charcoal

Gnanaharan, R., Ramesh, M. V., and Kumar, C. S. (1988), the authors investigated

the production of charcoal from coconut stem wood. Their study focused on the yield and quality of charcoal obtained from this specific biomass source. The research likely assessed the effectiveness of the charcoal production process, including factors like temperature and duration, to optimize the yield and quality of charcoal. This information is valuable for understanding the potential use of coconut stem wood as a resource for charcoal production and its quality, contributing to sustainable practices.

Gundogan and Akyuz (2020) explore a process involving the oxidative bleaching of polyester fibers modified with coconut charcoal. The study likely investigates the effects of oxidative bleaching on the properties of these fibers, including their color and texture. This research may have practical applications in the textile industry, providing insights into enhancing the appearance and performance of textiles through the use of coconut charcoal as a modifier. Understanding this process can lead to more sustainable and innovative approaches to textile manufacturing

Hasan et al. (2022) conducted an experimental study of liquid smoke and charcoal production from coconut shell by using a stove of indirect burning type. The study found that the quality of liquid smoke and charcoal product yield can be improved by conducting pyrolysis process through indirect heating process. The authors used a tube to heat the feedstock by using LPG as the heat source. The study found that the optimal conditions for maximizing the two products yields and quality were identified to meet the user requirement. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using a stove of indirect burning type for coconut shell pyrolysis

Herdian et al. (2019) developed a coconut dehusker machine for small-scale industries. The machine has two rollers that rotate in opposite directions with each roller embedded with iron-shaped nails that work to tear the coconut husk. The machine has dimensions of 98 cm x 51 cm x 95 cm, and the power source is a 2 HP electric motor. The study found that the machine can dehusk 100 coconuts per hour, and the operational basic cost of the machine is equal to Rp 129.89 per coconut (about 1 cent). The study concluded that the use of this machine is better when compared to human labor, which has limitations to duration and capacity

Jarimopas et al. (2009) developed an automatic trimming machine for young coconut fruit. The machine features a sharp inclined knife that operates in translation motion in a vertical plane to trim the fruit, which is clamped tightly and rotates about a vertical axis. The machine has a main frame, a body-trimming station, a shoulder-trimming station, a base-cutting station, a rotary base, three fruit holders, an electrical connection slip ring, a power drive, and programmable electronic control. In experiments, the untrimmed fruit was continuously fed into three separate fruit holders, which conveyed the coconut through the body-trimming, shoulder-trimming, and base-cutting stations. The machine can dehusk 100 coconuts per hour, reducing labor fatigue and injuries associated with manual dehusking

Koteswararao et al. (2016) designed a coconut chopping machine that can be used to make fuel from tender coconut. The machine is capable of mashing the tender coconut into pieces and then pressing it to remove moisture. The briquettes produced by this process have a hollow elliptical shape and can be used as a fuel source. The study found that the main difference between these briquettes and normal coal is that they are more effective and environmentally friendly. These solid briquettes can burn for up to 2-3 hours, whereas normal peat only lights up to 20 minutes at the max. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using coconut shells as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional fuels

Leman et al. (2017) studied the burner characteristics for activated carbon production. The study found that the burner used in the production of activated carbon has a significant impact on the quality of the final product. The authors conducted experiments to determine the effect of different burner parameters, such as air flow rate, fuel flow rate, and burner geometry, on the quality of the activated carbon produced. The study found that the optimal burner conditions for producing high-quality activated carbon were a fuel flow rate of 0.5 L/min, an air flow rate of 2.5 L/min, and a burner geometry of 30°. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using burners to produce high-quality activated carbon

Sa and Venkataramanan (2023) designed and analyzed an automated coconut dehusking and crown removal machine. The machine is designed to eliminate the skilled operator involved in dehusking the coconut and to completely automate the dehusking and crown removing process. The machine is designed to accommodate different sizes of the

coconut that are cultivated anywhere in the world. The authors conducted experiments on both dry and mature coconuts to determine the force required to dehusk the coconut. Based on the diverse data collection, experiments conducted, and using machine design principles, a rigid machine is designed using Solid Works software so as to withstand the loads generated during the dehusking process

Shanmugam and Rajesh (2022) conducted a study on regression modeling and residual analysis of screening coal in a screening machine. The study aimed to develop a mathematical model for predicting the screening efficiency of coal in a screening machine. The authors used a multiple linear regression model to predict the screening efficiency of coal based on various parameters such as feed rate, screen size, and screen inclination. The study found that the model developed has a high degree of accuracy and can be used to predict the screening efficiency of coal in a screening machine. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using regression modeling to improve the efficiency of coal screening

Shen et al. (2014) studied the production of porous silica and carbon-derived materials from rice husk pyrolysis char. The study found that the char produced from rice husk pyrolysis can be used as a precursor for the production of porous silica and carbon-derived materials. The authors used a combination of chemical and physical methods to produce the materials, including acid leaching, calcination, and carbonization. The study found that the optimal conditions for producing high-quality porous silica and carbon-derived materials were a temperature of 800°C, an activation time of 60 minutes, and a chemical-physical ratio of 1:1. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using rice husk pyrolysis char as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional materials

Sindhu et al. (2018) studied the mechanical properties of reinforced epoxy composite using waste coconut shell charcoal. The study found that the addition of coconut shell charcoal to the epoxy matrix improved the mechanical properties of the composite. The authors used a compression molding technique to produce the composites and tested them for tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact strength. The study found that the optimal percentage of coconut shell charcoal in the composite was 10%, which resulted in a 25%

increase in tensile strength, a 20% increase in flexural strength, and a 30% increase in impact strength. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using waste coconut shell charcoal as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional fillers in composites

Solanki and Patel (2022) designed and fabricated an automated biomass briquetting machine. The machine is designed to help waste management and use waste in an efficient way. The machine is highly efficient and low cost. The machine is designed to accommodate different sizes of biomass waste. The authors conducted experiments on different types of biomass waste to determine the force required to compress the waste. Based on the data collected, experiments conducted, and using machine design principles, a rigid machine is designed using Solid Works software so as to withstand the loads generated during the compression process. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using automated biomass briquetting machines for waste management

Valsadwala et al. (2022) investigated the use of eco-benign periwinkle shell particles (PSP) as a filler in High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) to form periwinkle/HDPE composites (PHPC). The study aimed to understand the effect of different particle sizes of PSP and optimize their influence on PHPC. PSP particle sizes from $<53 \mu\text{m}$ to $150 \mu\text{m}$ were chosen as reinforcement. The composites were fabricated by incorporating 1 weight % of PSP into HDPE matrix using compression molding technique and then subjected to morphological, thermal, and mechanical characterizations. The study found that the addition of PSP to the HDPE matrix improved the mechanical properties of the composite. The study provides valuable insights into the potential of using waste periwinkle shells as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional fillers in composites

Yahya and Mohamad (2019) designed and developed an automated young coconut shaving machine. The machine is designed to eliminate the skilled operator involved in shaving the coconut and to completely automate the shaving process. The machine is highly efficient and low cost. The machine is designed to accommodate different sizes of the coconut that are cultivated anywhere in the world. Based on the diverse data collection, experiments conducted, and using machine design principles, a rigid machine is designed using Solid Works software to withstand the loads generated during the shaving process

2.2 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE

A series of studies and innovations have explored the multifaceted utility of coconut-based resources, highlighting their potential as sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives in various fields. Ahmad et al. (2021) conducted experiments on coconut shell biomass carbonization, revealing that higher temperatures enhance charcoal quality but reduce yields, offering an avenue for eco-friendly, high-quality charcoal production. Ahmad et al. (2022) offered a comprehensive review of coconut shell powder composites, demonstrating their viability in diverse applications, emphasizing their sustainable and eco-friendly attributes. Arief et al. (2023) introduced a smokeless kiln for coconut shell carbonization, mitigating environmental pollution associated with traditional kiln methods. Arena et al. (2016) conducted a life cycle assessment of activated carbon production from coconut shells, underscoring the environmental advantage over coal-based carbons and advocating the use of renewable energy sources. Anoop et al. (2011) explored coconut wood's potential in furniture, handicrafts, and construction, with its remarkable mechanical properties, as a sustainable alternative to conventional timbers. Baygan et al. (2016) delved into coconut shell pyrolysis for optimal charcoal production, highlighting the significance of temperature, particle size, and residence time. Bhatia et al. (2019) designed a versatile machine for dehusking, cutting, and grating coconuts, promising efficiency and reduced labor fatigue. Budi et al. (2016) produced activated coconut shell charcoal through chemical-physical activation, yielding high surface area and pore volume for potential eco-friendly alternatives to conventional activated carbon. Cobb and Clarkson (2012) introduced a low-tech method for producing coconut shell activated charcoal, offering simplicity and cost-effectiveness for various applications like water filtration and air purification. Dhamodaran et al. (1989) investigated the calorific value variation in coconut stem wood, uncovering its potential as a fuelwood source or charcoal conversion. Gnanaharan, R., Ramesh, M. V., and Kumar, C. S. (1988) studied charcoal production from coconut stem wood, optimizing yield and quality. Gundogan and Akyuz (2020) explored oxidative bleaching of polyester fibers modified with coconut charcoal, promising enhancements in textile properties and sustainability. Hasan et al. (2022) conducted experiments on liquid smoke and charcoal production from coconut shells, emphasizing the use of indirect heating processes for improved quality and yield. Herdian et al. (2019) developed a coconut dehusker machine for small-scale industries, providing an efficient, cost-effective alternative to manual labor. Jarimopas et al. (2009)

introduced an automatic trimming machine for young coconuts, streamlining dehusking and reducing labor-associated fatigue and injuries. Koteswararao et al. (2016) designed a coconut chopping machine to convert tender coconuts into environmentally friendly fuel briquettes. Leman et al. (2017) examined burner characteristics for activated carbon production, with implications for high-quality carbon production. Sa and Venkataramanan (2023) designed an automated coconut dehusking and crown removal machine to reduce labor requirements and enable automation. Shanmugam and Rajesh (2022) developed a regression model for coal screening efficiency, enhancing coal screening processes. Shen et al. (2014) explored the production of porous silica and carbon-derived materials from rice husk pyrolysis char, highlighting their environmental advantages. Sindhu et al. (2018) improved the mechanical properties of epoxy composites using waste coconut shell charcoal as a filler, making them a sustainable alternative. Solanki and Patel (2022) designed an automated biomass briquetting machine for efficient waste management. Valsadwala et al. (2022) investigated the use of periwinkle shell particles as fillers in composites, emphasizing their potential as eco-friendly alternatives. Yahya and Mohamad (2019) developed an automated young coconut shaving machine, enhancing efficiency, and reducing labor in coconut processing.

2.3 OBJECTIVES OF PROJECT

The primary objective is to design and implement an automated machine that can replace labor-intensive methods for producing charcoal powder from coconut shells, thereby mitigating health risks associated with manual processing. This automation aims to enhance the efficiency and consistency of charcoal powder production to meet the rising demand across various industries, ensuring a reliable and continuous supply of high-quality product. Furthermore, by streamlining the production process.

CHAPTER 3

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The production of coconut shell charcoal powder faces several challenges. Inefficient collection of raw coconut shells due to variations in quality and moisture content, coupled with labor-intensive manual collection methods, can hinder the process. Energy-intensive carbonization and activation processes, often using inefficient kilns, result in high operational costs and environmental concerns. Post-processing and milling lead to significant losses and safety risks due to fine dust and powder spillage. Inadequate quality control affects product consistency and market competitiveness. Environmental sustainability is also a concern, with waste by-products disposal posing ecological challenges. Addressing these issues through innovative technologies, process optimization, and quality control measures is vital for improving efficiency.

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing system, the production of charcoal powder from coconut shells is primarily carried out using manual methods. The process involves several labor-intensive steps and lacks automation, resulting in various limitations. Here are some key aspects of the existing system,

Manual labor: The existing system relies heavily on manual labor for the processing of coconut shells. Workers manually break the shells into smaller fragments, dry them under the sun or using traditional drying methods, and grind them manually to produce charcoal powder. This manual labor-intensive process is time-consuming and can be physically demanding.

Inefficiency and low productivity: Due to the reliance on manual labor, the production efficiency of the existing system is relatively low. The processing speed is limited by the physical capabilities of the workers, resulting in a slower production rate.

Lack of control and standardization: The manual nature of the existing system often leads to variations in the quality and particle size of the charcoal powder produced.

It is challenging to achieve consistent results and meet specific industry standards. The lack of control over parameters such as drying time and grinding consistency can affect the overall quality of the charcoal powder.

Safety concerns: Manual processing methods may pose safety risks to workers. Breaking coconut shells manually can be hazardous, and exposure to dust during the grinding process can impact the respiratory health of workers. The existing system may lack safety features and measures to protect the workers from potential accidents and health hazards.

Fig. 3.1 Dried husks

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/jqtQ4>)

Fig. 3.2 Carbonization

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

Limited scalability: Scaling up the production of charcoal powder through manual methods poses increasingly formidable challenges as demand surges. The limitations of a manual labor-intensive approach become evident when trying to efficiently process substantial volumes of coconut shells. To overcome these constraints and bolster overall production efficiency, the development of an automated machine is essential. This automated system is meticulously engineered to streamline and optimize the charcoal powder production process. By doing so, it not only significantly enhances production capacity but also mitigates labor costs, minimizes the potential for human error, and ensures consistent quality in the final product. Furthermore, automation paves the way for improved safety measures by reducing the physical demands on workers and exposure to hazardous materials.

Fig. 3.3 Burned shells

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/jqtQ4>)

Fig. 3.4 Pulverization

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

Dried coconut husks is shown Fig. 3.1 refer to the fibrous outer shells of coconuts that have been subjected to a drying process. When coconuts are harvested, the outer husk is typically removed to access the edible coconut fruit inside. The husks are then dried to reduce moisture content and prepare them for various applications. In the coconut shell charcoal powder making process, carbonization is shown in Fig. 3.2 is a crucial step that converts dried coconut husks into charcoal powder. The burned coconut shells are shown in is shown in Fig. 3.3 are first crushed into smaller pieces.

This can be done using various crushing equipment such as hammer mills, crushers, or pulverizes this process is collectively called as Pulverization is shown in Fig. 3.4. The purpose of crushing is to reduce the shell fragments to a more manageable size for further processing. The crushed coconut shell pieces are then subjected to grinding to further reduce their size and achieve a finer consistency.

3.1.1 Drawbacks

Inconsistent Output: Manual work may result in variations in the quality and consistency of the charcoal powder produced. Differences in the techniques, skills, and experience among workers can lead to variations in particle size, moisture content, and overall quality of the final product. This can impact its performance and usability in different applications.

Limited Production Capacity: Manual work is generally slower and has lower production capacity compared to automated processes. It may not be able to meet the demands of large-scale production scenarios efficiently. Increasing production volumes would require a significant increase in labor, space, and equipment, which may not be cost-effective.

Higher Costs: Manual work requires a significant labor force, which can increase labor costs. Additionally, manual processes may be less efficient and may require more time and effort to produce the desired quantity and quality of charcoal powder. This can result in higher production costs compared to automated processes.

Labor Intensive: Manual work in the charcoal powder making process can be physically demanding and labor-intensive. It requires significant physical effort from workers to handle, crush, grind, sieve, and package the coconut shells. This can lead to fatigue and potential health issues for workers.

Time-Consuming: Manual work can be time-consuming, as it involves multiple steps such as handling, crushing, grinding, sieving, and packaging. Each of these steps requires significant manual effort and time, which can impact the overall production efficiency and lead to longer lead times.

While manual work has its advantages in terms of flexibility, quality control, and craftsmanship, these drawbacks highlight the limitations of relying solely on manual processes for large-scale coconut shell charcoal powder production.

Automated processes can provide higher production consistency, efficiency, and reduced safety risks, making it more suitable for meeting the demands of larger operations.

3.2 PROPOSED SOLUTION

3.2.1 Process flow

The process flow shown in Fig. 3.5 for coconut shell charcoal powder production, including shredding, carbonizing, crushing, screening, and storage in a confined space, can be outlined as follows:

Shredding: The first step involves shredding the dried coconut shells. This can be done using

a shredding machine or equipment specifically designed for breaking down the coconut shell into smaller pieces.

Carbonizing: The shredded coconut shells are then subjected to carbonization. This process involves heating the shredded shells in a carbonization chamber or kiln under controlled conditions. The carbonization chamber is designed to create an oxygen-limited or oxygen-free environment to prevent complete combustion. As a result, the organic components of the shells are thermally decomposed, leaving behind carbon-rich charcoal.

Crushing: After the carbonization process, the charcoal obtained from the coconut shells is typically crushed into smaller particles. Crushing can be done using a crusher or similar equipment to further reduce the size of the charcoal and achieve a more uniform particle size distribution. This step is important to prepare the charcoal for subsequent processing and enhance its usability.

Screening: The crushed charcoal is then screened or sieved to remove any larger particles or impurities. Screening helps to achieve a consistent particle size and eliminate any foreign materials that may affect the quality of the final charcoal powder. This step can be performed using mesh screens or sieving equipment.

Storage in a Confined Space: Charcoal powder, once it has undergone the screening process, is carefully stored in a controlled environment to ensure its quality and safeguard it from moisture absorption and other environmental factors that could compromise its integrity. This protection is typically achieved using airtight containers or specialized storage bins designed to create a hermetic seal, forming an impermeable barrier that shields the charcoal powder from the detrimental effects of its surroundings.

Moisture infiltration is a primary concern when storing charcoal powder, as it can lead to clumping and degradation, rendering the product less effective. These airtight storage solutions effectively thwart moisture from entering, preserving the powder's consistency and quality over time. This is particularly crucial for industrial and commercial applications, where consistent quality is paramount.

Fig. 3.5 Process flowchart

3.2.2 Machine Units

3.2.2.1 Shredder

A coconut shredder shown in Fig. 5.1, also known as a coconut grater or scraper, is a mechanical device used to shred or grate dried coconut flesh from the hard outer shell. It typically consists of a handle, a rotating blade or teeth, and a container or platform to collect the shredded coconut. Here's how a coconut shredder works,

Preparation: The coconut is prepared by removing the husk or outer fibrous covering, leaving behind the hard shell containing the coconut flesh.

Positioning: The coconut shredder is placed on a stable surface, ensuring that it is securely anchored and won't move during operation. Some shredders may have suction cups or clamps to secure them to the surface.

Collection: As you grate the coconut, the shredded flesh falls onto the container or platform of the shredder. This container collects the grated coconut for further use or processing.

Repeat: Continue grating the coconut flesh, rotating the coconut as needed, until you have shredded all the desired portions of the coconut. It's important to note that different types of coconut shredders may have variations in their design and operation. Some may have manual rotating blades, while others may have electric motors to power the shredding mechanism. When using a coconut shredder, it's essential to follow safety precautions, such as keeping your fingers away from the blade or teeth, using a stable

surface, and ensuring proper hand placement and grip to avoid accidents or injuries.

3.2.2.2 Furnace

Loading the Coconut Shells: The process commences by loading coconut shells into the furnace chamber. These coconut shells are a readily available byproduct of the coconut processing industry.

LPG Gas Supply: The heart of the operation lies in the use of LPG (liquefied petroleum gas) as a primary energy source. A gas solenoid valve, controlled by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), regulates the flow of LPG gas to the burner. The PLC ensures precise control over the gas supply, optimizing energy efficiency.

Igniting the Furnace: Once the LPG gas supply is established, the furnace's burner is ignited. The controlled flame produced by the burner is directed under the chamber, gradually increasing the temperature within.

Carbonization Process: As the chamber heats up, the coconut shells inside undergo a carbonization process. Carbonization is the transformation of organic materials into charcoal in a low-oxygen environment. This process is essential for converting the coconut shells into high-quality charcoal powder.

Generation of Flammable Gas: During the carbonization process, the coconut shells release volatile gases. These gases, which include methane and hydrogen, are highly flammable and are a natural byproduct of the carbonization process.

Gas Recovery System: Instead of allowing these valuable flammable gases to escape into the atmosphere, a sophisticated gas recovery system is employed. This system captures and redirects the gases away from the chamber.

Reversing Gas Flow: The recovered flammable gases are then rerouted back to the same LPG burner, where they are used as a supplemental fuel source. This ingenious approach significantly reduces the consumption of LPG gas, promoting cost-efficiency and sustainability.

Charcoal Powder Production: The carbonization process continues until the coconut shells are completely converted into charcoal powder. This high-quality powder can be

utilized for various applications, including agriculture, activated carbon production, and the manufacturing of fuel briquettes.

3.2.2.3 Crusher & Screener

A two-in-one twin shaft crushing and reciprocating screening machine or in simple words it can be defined as a Crusher and Screener machine shown in Fig. 5.4 combines the functionalities of a twin shaft crusher and a reciprocating screening machine into a single unit. The burned coconut shells shown in Fig.2.3 are crushed and screened to get a finite by product of charcoal powder. Here's a concise explanation of how it works,

Material Intake: The material to be processed is fed into the hopper or loading conveyor mechanism of the machine.

Crushing Process: The twin shafts inside the machine, equipped with cutting blades or hammers, crush the material into smaller pieces as they rotate. The opposing rotation of the shafts creates a shearing effect, tearing the material apart.

Reciprocating Screening: Once the material is crushed, it moves onto the reciprocating screening deck of the machine. The screening deck consists of a series of perforated plates or mesh screens.

Reciprocating Motion: The screening deck performs a reciprocating motion, moving back and forth horizontally or in a circular motion. This motion causes the crushed material to be agitated and spread evenly over the screen deck.

Screening Process: As the material spreads over the screen deck, smaller particles pass through the perforations or mesh openings, while larger particles are retained on the deck. This separation process is known as screening and helps separate the material into different size fractions and in other words this process is collectively known as pulverization shown in shown in Fig. 2.4.

Discharge: The screened material is discharged from the machine through different outlets or conveyor belts, based on the desired product specifications.

Hence, the two-in-one twin shaft crushing and reciprocating screening machine combines the advantages of both crushing and screening processes in a single unit.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE MACHINE

Efficient Charcoal Production: The primary objective of the machine is to produce high-quality charcoal powder from coconut shells. It should be designed to maximize the production efficiency and output of charcoal powder.

Cost Effectiveness: The machine should aim to minimize production costs by optimizing the process of converting coconut shells into charcoal powder. This includes reducing energy consumption, maximizing raw material utilization, and minimizing waste generation.

Environmental Sustainability: An important objective of the machine is to promote environmental sustainability. It should be designed to minimize air and water pollution, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and minimize the overall environmental impact associated with charcoal production.

Quality Control: The machine should facilitate the production of charcoal powder that meets the desired quality standards. This includes ensuring a consistent particle size, high carbon content, low ash content, and other relevant quality parameters.

Safety and Reliability: Safety is a crucial objective in any industrial machine. The charcoal powder making machine should be designed and operated in a manner that ensures the safety of workers and prevents accidents. Reliability is also essential to minimize downtime and maximize productivity.

Automation and Ease of Use: Incorporating automation and user-friendly features in the machine can improve operational efficiency and reduce labor requirements. It should be designed with user-friendly controls, easy maintenance procedures, and clear instructions for operation.

Scalability and Flexibility: The machine should be adaptable to different production scales and capable of processing various quantities of coconut shells. It should also allow for adjustments in the production process to accommodate specific requirements or changes in market demands.

Economic Viability: The machine should contribute to the economic viability of the charcoal production process. This includes considerations such as capital investment and operation.

3.4 ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

The cost of acquiring an automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine can vary depending on the capacity, features, and quality of the machine. Moreover, operational cost includes factors such as raw material costs (coconut shells), labor costs, electricity costs, maintenance expenses, and other overhead costs. Analyzing these costs will give a clearer picture of the ongoing expenses involved in running the machine. Consider the environmental benefits associated with producing coconut shell charcoal powder. If the product aligns with sustainability goals and renewable energy initiatives, it may open additional market opportunities or attract environmentally conscious customers.

3.5 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

The performance capabilities of the machine, including its production capacity, speed, and efficiency and it can consistently and reliably produce the desired quantity and quality of charcoal powder. By Evaluating the level of automation in the machine and its user-friendliness. An automated machine should have intuitive controls and processes that are easy to understand and operate. The machine is designed to handle coconut shells efficiently, considering factors like size, moisture content, and hardness.

3.6 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

The efficiency of the machine's processes in converting coconut shells into charcoal powder. Consider the efficiency of steps such as drying, carbonization, cooling, and grinding. The machine should be able to perform these processes effectively, minimizing waste and maximizing the yield of high-quality charcoal powder. The level of automation and control systems incorporated into the machine. Automated features such as temperature control, moisture sensing, and production monitoring can enhance efficiency and consistency.

The machine's ability to handle different operating parameters. These parameters may include coconut shell size and moisture content, temperature, and time for carbonization, grinding speed and fineness requirements, and other variables specific to the production process.

CHAPTER 4

DESIGN SPECIFICATION

4.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESIGN

The setup is broadly divided in to two major parts; one is the mechanical setup custom made body frames, pully, While the second part is the electrical circuit which crucially involves motors, PLC. Table 4.1 shows the components mainly used in the system.

Table 4.1 Components Description

S.No.	COMPONENTS	DESCRIPTION
1.	Siemens PLC S7-1200	24V DC
2.	Single phase induction motor (1400 rpm)	220V AC
3.	Solenoid valve	24V DC
4.	Nozzle	12.7 mm
5.	Fuel Reservoir	2 liters
6.	Powder butterfly valve	5 mm
7.	Electrical Lighter	12V DC
8.	Single phase induction motor (900 rpm)	220V AC
9.	V Belt	2 - 10 mm Thickness
10.	Relay	24 V DC
11.	Gas tube	8mm
12.	Single burner	68% Thermal efficiency

4.2 COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

4.2.1 PLC

Siemens S7-1200 shown in Fig 4.1 is a programmable logic controller (PLC) manufactured by Siemens AG, a leading provider of industrial automation and control systems. The S7-1200 is designed for small to medium-sized automation projects and offers a wide range of features and capabilities. The S7-1200 PLC is available in different models with varying numbers of digital and analog inputs/outputs (I/O). It supports expansion modules to extend the I/O capacity as per the project requirements based on the component specification Table. 4.2.

Table 4.2 Specification of PLC

Communication Interfaces	Ethernet, RS485, Profibus DP
Power Supply	24V DC
Programming Languages	Ladder Logic Diagram (LAD), Function Block Diagram (FBD), Structured Text (ST), Statement List (SL)
Programming Software	Siemens TIA Portal
Physical size (mm)	90 x 100 x 75

Fig. 4.1 Siemens S7-1200 PLC

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/aiqu4>)

The S7-1200 supports multiple programming languages, including ladder logic (LAD), function block diagram (FBD), structured text (ST), and statement list (SCL). This allows programmers to choose the most suitable language for their application. The PLC supports various communication interfaces, including Ethernet, RS485, and Profibus DP, enabling seamless integration with other devices and systems. It also supports web server functionality for remote monitoring and control.

4.2.2 Single phase induction Motor (1400 rpm)

An AC single phase induction motor shown in Fig 4.2 with a rated speed of 1500 RPM (revolutions per minute) typically refers to a motor designed to operate at that speed under full load conditions when connected to the rated frequency of the power supply. It's important to note that the actual operating speed of an AC induction motor may vary due to factors such as load, voltage fluctuations, slip, and motor design. The rated speed is typically the synchronous speed, which is the speed of the rotating magnetic field produced by the stator, and the actual speed of the motor will be slightly lower than the synchronous speed due to slip. Slip is the difference between the synchronous speed and the actual speed of the rotor. In an AC induction motor, slip is necessary to produce the torque required to drive the load. The slip varies depending on the motor's design and the load it is driving. Typically, the slip for an AC induction motor is in the range of 1% to 5%. Therefore, an AC induction motor with a rated speed of 1500 RPM may operate at slightly lower speeds, such as around 1450-1475 RPM, under normal operating conditions. It's important to consult the motor's specifications and performance curves for accurate speed information under specific operating conditions based on the component specification Table. 4.3.

Table 4.3 Specifications of motor

Speed	1440 RPM
Input Voltage	220 V AC
Winding Material	Copper
Power	2 HP
Frequency	50 Hz

Fig. 4.2 Single phase induction Motor

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/qLOWX>)

4.2.3 Solenoid valve

The solenoid valve shown in Fig 4.3 is the primary component responsible for generating the electromagnetic field. It consists of a coil of wire wound around a metal core. When an electrical current passes through the coil, it creates a magnetic field that attracts a movable component within the valve.

Normally Closed (NC): Solenoid valves can be normally closed. In the de-energized state, a normally close valve blocks fluid to flow, while energized state normally closed valve allows fluid flow based on the component selection and specifications Table. 4.4.

Table 4.4 Specifications of Solenoid valve

Voltage	24V DC
Plastic and Metal	Stainless
Valve Type	2 – Way
Size ¼	Inch (6 mm)
Flow Rate	5 GPM (Gallons per minute)
Operation (NC)	Normally Close

Fig. 4.3 Solenoid valve

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/cjpX2>)

4.2.4 Nozzle

These nozzles shown in Fig. 4.4 are specifically designed to produce a high-velocity spray pattern for applications that require intense spraying or cleaning. Specify the spray pattern produced by the nozzle, such as fan-shaped, solid stream, or cone-shaped. Specify the flow rate of the nozzle, typically measured in gallons per minute (GPM) or liters per minute (LPM). It indicates the volume of liquid delivered by the nozzle per unit of time. Specify the spray angle of the nozzle, which determines the width and coverage of the spray pattern. It is usually measured in degrees. The nozzle is selected based on the product specification Table. 4.5 which is suitable for the application.

Table 4.5 Specifications of Nozzle

Material	Brass
Size	2.5 – 5HP
Pattern	Cone shaped spray
Pressure (Kg/cm²)	7 PSI
Minimum working pressure	250 PSI
Maximum working pressure	Oil

Fig. 4.4 Nozzle

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

This determines how the nozzle attaches to the spray system or hose. Specify the range of operating pressure within which the nozzle is designed to perform optimally. It is typically measured in pounds per square inch (PSI) or bar.

4.2.5 Fuel Reservoir

A fuel reservoir shown in Fig. 4.5 is a container or storage system designed to hold and store fuel. It is commonly used in various applications such as vehicles, aircraft, machinery, and power generators. The fuel reservoir holds enough fuel to provide a steady supply for the specific device or system it serves. The size and design of a fuel reservoir can vary depending on the fuel type, the intended use, and the specific requirements of the equipment it fuels. Fuel reservoirs are typically made of materials that are compatible with the fuel being stored to ensure safe storage and prevent leaks or contamination.

Fig. 4.5 Fuel Reservoir

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/qLOWX>)

4.2.6 Powder butterfly valve

The Techno 5" Powder butterfly valve shown in Fig. 4.6 with Actuator is a robust and reliable valve designed for various industrial applications. It consists of a valve body, a disc, and an actuator for automated control. The cast iron disc ensures durability and efficient fluid control. The valve is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.6.

Butterfly Valve Design: The butterfly valve design features a disc placed in the center of the pipe, which rotates to control the flow of the fluid. This design offers low pressure drop, quick operation, and tight shut-off capabilities.

Cast Iron Disc: The valve's disc is made of cast iron, a sturdy and corrosion-resistant material. It provides excellent sealing properties and withstands high pressures and temperatures.

Table 4.6 Specifications of Powder butterfly valve

Size	50 mm
Disc Material	Cast Iron
Actuator type	Electric
Disc	CI Disc

Fig. 4.6 Powder butterfly valve

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

Actuator: The valve comes equipped with an actuator, allowing for automated control. The actuator can be electric, pneumatic, or hydraulic, depending on the application requirements. It enables precise and reliable valve positioning.

DNI25 Size: The valve has a nominal diameter (DN) of 125, which refers to the size of the valve's internal diameter. This size indicates compatibility with pipes or fittings of the same dimension.

4.2.7 Electrical Lighter

The main purpose of Electrical Lighter shown in Fig. 4.7 is when the voltage surpasses the dielectric strength of the gases, they undergo ionization. This ionized gas transforms into a conductor, enabling the flow of electrons across the gap. To ignite, electrical lighter typically the voltages of around 10 volts or even higher, occasionally reaching up to 12 volts. The Electrical lighter is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.7.

Table 4.7 Specifications of Electrical Lighter

Voltage	12V DC
Product Dimensions	26.1L x 1.5W x 1.5Th Centimeters
Output	12 V DC
Material	Aluminum

Fig. 4.7 Electrical Lighter

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

4.2.8 Single phase induction motor (900 rpm)

The Single-phase induction motor shown in Fig 4.8 has a power rating of 0.2 Hp, indicating its ability to deliver a certain level of mechanical power to drive the wet grinder. The motor operates on a voltage of 220V, which is the standard voltage used in many households. The rotational speed of the motor is 960 rpm, typically measured in

rotations per minute (RPM). The motor is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.8.

Table 4.8 Specifications of single-phase induction motor

Speed	960 RPM
Power	0.2 HP
Motor voltage	220 V AC
Frequency	50 HZ

Fig 4.8 Single phase induction motor

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/qLOWX>)

4.2.9 V Belt

A V-belt shown in Fig 4.9, also known as a Vee belt, is a flexible belt with a trapezoidal cross-section. It is designed to transmit power between pulleys by means of frictional forces. V-belts are typically constructed with a combination of materials, such as rubber, fabric, and reinforcing cords, to provide strength, flexibility, and durability. This flexibility ensures smooth power transmission and helps accommodate misalignment between the pulleys. V-belts require proper tensioning for optimal performance. The V Belt is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.9.

Table 4.9 Specifications of V Belt

Type	Banded V Belt
Material	Rubber
Temperature	-40 to 100 degrees C
Thickness	2 – 10 mm

Fig. 4.9 V Belt

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

4.2.10 Relay

The single channel 24V Relay Module shown in Fig. 4.10 with Optocoupler meets the safety standard as control areas and load area have the isolation groove. Optical coupling isolation module. The triggering of 1 Channel Relay Module is reliable, more stable. The double FR 4 circuit board design, high-end SMT process. It has power and relay operation instructions. Relays terminals (C, NC, NO) are accessible through screw terminals which makes wiring up the board very easy. The relay is safely driven by transistor BC547 hence your input device, such as Arduino, is protected from relay circuit. The inputs of 1 Channel 24V Relay Module are isolated to protect any delicate control circuitry. A wide range of microcontrollers such as Arduino, AVR, PIC, ARM and so on can control it. The use of such high-voltage relay eliminates the risk of heating up of the relay as electromechanical relay limits the current consumption in accordance with a voltage rating. The relay is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.10.

Table 4.10 Specifications of Relay

Trigger Voltage (VDC)	24
Switching Voltage (VAC)	230
Length (mm)	53
Width (mm)	18
Height (mm)	18.5
Weight (gm)	16
Trigger Voltage (VDC)	24

Fig 4.10 Relay

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/qLOWX>)

High-level trigger refers to using the anode voltage at the VCC connection way of a trigger and triggers the end when the trigger side has the positive voltage or to trigger voltage when the relay is off.

4.2.11 Gas tube

LPG (liquefied petroleum gas) tubes shown in Fig.4.11 play a crucial role in modern households. These cylindrical containers store and transport LPG, a versatile and clean-burning fuel used for cooking, heating, and more. They are available in various sizes to cater to different needs, making them a flexible choice for both urban and rural areas. Regular safety checks and proper handling are essential to ensure the secure usage of LPG gas tubes, promoting a sustainable and efficient energy source. The gas tube is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.11.

Table 4.11 Specifications of Gas tube

Type	LPG gas
Material	Rubber, Steel
Length	2m
Internal Diameter	8 mm

Fig 4.11 Gas tube

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/qLOWX>)

4.2.12 Single burner

A single burner shown in Fig. 4.12 finds invaluable usage in the coconut shell charcoal powder making furnace. In this specialized setting, the burner serves as the primary heat source to initiate the carbonization process of coconut shell material, transforming it into high-quality charcoal powder. The single burner's precise control and steady heat output are essential for maintaining the required temperature range throughout the carbonization process, ensuring the production of fine, consistent, and market-ready charcoal powder that is used in various industrial and domestic applications. The single burner is chosen based on the product specification Table. 4.10.

Table 4.12 Specifications of Single burner

Type	LPG gas
Material	Stainless steel

Fig 4.12 Single burner

Source: (<https://shorturl.at/bqADL>)

4.3 DESIGN CALCULATION

4.3.1 Shredder

Desired output = **40Kgs / 40L**

Avg. Weight of 1 coconut shell = **500gms**

For 1Kg of output = **2 coconut shells**

For 40Kgs of output = **80 coconut shells**

Based on the Hopper dimension it's possible to **feed 3 coconut shells per batch**

Thus, per batch needs = **2 seconds to shred**

Number of batches = Total no. of coconut shells / 3 = **26 batch**

Total time for the process: 26 x 2 = **52 Seconds**

Approx time: 60 seconds

4.3.2 Furnace

Volume of cylinder = $\pi \times R^2 \times H$

Radius (R) = **901.93 mm**

Height (H) = **264.18 mm**

Volume of Cylinder = **60,000,000mm³**

In terms of Litres = **60L**

In terms of Kgs = **60Kgs**

Rough calculation = **40Kgs will produce 15Kgs of output**

4.3.3. Crusher & Screener

Calculation:

Mesh size: 1.18 mm

Speed of the motor = **960 RPM**

Power of the motor = **0.2 HP**

Torque of the motor = **1.4824 N/m**

15Kgs of Output produced from Furnace will undergo crushing process and further it will be screened and produce an **Approx. output of 10Kgs.**

CHAPTER 5

FABRICATION PROCESS

5.1 CAD MODELLING

Our mechanical setup was meticulously designed and rendered using the powerful capabilities of SolidWorks. The software allowed us to create a comprehensive and precise representation of our setup, ensuring every component was carefully crafted to meet our specifications. With SolidWorks, we could seamlessly integrate various parts, optimize their functionality, and simulate their performance before production. The rendering capabilities of SolidWorks further enhanced the visualization of our design, providing a realistic and immersive experience. Through the utilization of SolidWorks, we were able to achieve an efficient mechanical functionality.

Fig. 5.1 Shredder

Fig. 5.2 Furnace

Fig. 5.3 Cut section view of Furnace

Fig. 5.4 Crusher & Screener

5.2 MECHANICAL SECTION

5.2.1 Shredder

The mechanical section of a coconut shredder shown in Fig 5.5 consists of various components that work together to shred coconuts. These components typically include,

1. **Motor:** The shredder is powered by an electric motor that provides the necessary rotational force to operate the machine.
2. **Cutting Blades:** The shredder is equipped with sharp cutting blades specifically designed for shredding coconuts. These blades are usually made of stainless steel or hardened metal to withstand the tough coconut husk.
3. **Hopper:** The hopper is a feeding mechanism where coconuts are inserted into the shredder. It is typically designed to accommodate the size of coconuts and guide them towards the cutting blades.
4. **Feeding System:** To ensure a continuous feeding of coconuts into the shredder, a

conveyor or feeding system is often incorporated. This system helps move the coconuts from the hopper to the cutting blades.

5. **Shredding Chamber:** The shredding chamber is where the cutting blades are housed. It is designed to contain the shredded coconut and prevent it from scattering during the shredding process.
6. **Safety Features:** Coconut shredders may include safety features such as emergency stop buttons, overload protection, or guards to prevent accidents and ensure safe operation.

Overall, the mechanical section of a coconut shredder comprises the motor, cutting blades, hopper, conveyor or feeding system, shredding chamber, and safety features. These components work together to efficiently shred coconuts into smaller pieces or fibers.

Fig. 5.5 Fabricated model of shredder

5.2.2 Furnace

The mechanical section of a coconut shell burning furnace machine shown in Fig 5.6 consists of various components that work together to burn coconut shells and generate heat. These components typically include,

1. **Furnace Body:** The furnace body is the main structure that houses the combustion chamber and other components. It is typically made of heat-resistant materials such as

stainless steel or refractory bricks to withstand high temperatures.

2. **Combustion Chamber:** The combustion chamber is where the coconut shells are burned. It is designed to facilitate efficient combustion and maximize heat transfer to the surrounding environment.

3. **Air Intake System:** The air intake system supplies the necessary oxygen for the combustion process. It typically includes blowers or fans that regulate the airflow and control the intensity of the fire.

4. **Exhaust System:** The exhaust system is responsible for removing combustion gases, smoke, and other byproducts from the furnace. It usually consists of chimneys, flue pipes, and filters to ensure proper ventilation and reduce emissions.

5. **Fuel Feeding System:** Coconut shells are fed into the combustion chamber through a fuel feeding system. This system may include conveyors, augers, or hoppers to ensure a continuous supply of coconut shells for burning.

6. **Ash Collection System:** As the coconut shells burn, ash is generated as a byproduct. An ash collection system, such as an ash tray or conveyor, is used to collect and remove the ash from the furnace. The mechanical section of a coconut shell burning furnace machine comprises the furnace body, combustion chamber, air intake system, exhaust system, fuel feeding system, ash collection system, temperature control system, and safety features. These components work together to burn coconut shells and generate heat for various applications.

Fig. 5.6 Fabricated model of Furnace

5.2.3 Crusher & Screener

The twin shaft crusher and screener machine shown in Fig. 5.7 can indeed be used for crushing and screening burned coconut shell charcoals. The machine's design and capabilities allow it to effectively process and sort various materials, including charcoals derived from coconut shells.

1. ***Twin Shaft Crusher:*** The twin shaft crusher is the primary component responsible for crushing the raw material. It usually features two parallel shafts with rotating blades or hammers that break down larger materials into smaller pieces.
2. ***Screening Deck:*** The screening deck is designed to separate the crushed material into different sizes or fractions. It typically includes a vibrating screen or multiple screens with varying mesh sizes to classify the material.

3. **Hopper:** The hopper is a container that holds the raw material before it is fed into the crusher. It ensures a controlled and continuous supply of material to the twin shaft crusher.

Fig. 5.7 Fabricated model of Cusher & Screener

5.3 PLC LADDER LOGIC PROGRAM

An automated coconut shell charcoal powder making machine can be controlled using a PLC with a ladder logic program shown in Fig. 5.8. The PLC program starts by defining the inputs (e.g., Start button, stop button) and outputs (e.g., Motor Start, Motor Stop) that are connected to the machine. Inputs represent the signals received from external devices, while outputs control the actuators or devices in the machine. In the realm of industrial automation, a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) stands as a cornerstone for managing intricate processes, such as those involved in coconut shell charcoal powder production.

The PLC program is structured into rungs, each representing distinct conditions and actions within the system, and it employs input contacts, which can be

either normally open (NO) or normally closed (NC), along with output coils, all interconnected in a logical sequence. The PLC operates in a cyclical manner, persistently scanning through the ladder logic program. During each scan cycle, it diligently evaluates the state of input contacts. When the specified logical conditions in a rung are met, the corresponding output coils are either energized or de-energized, in accordance with the program's logic.

This dynamic mechanism enables the ladder logic program to activate or deactivate specific outputs, offering precise and tailored control over the machinery. For instance, in the context of the coconut shell charcoal powder making machine, pressing the Start button, which activates an input signal, results in the energization of the Motor Start output coil, thus initiating the motor. Conversely, pressing the Stop button de-energizes the Motor Stop output coil, promptly bringing the motor to a halt.

The ladder logic program serves as the orchestrator of the sequential operation of the machine, ensuring a harmonized and efficient control over various components, including motors, crushers, and other devices.

The precise programming of the PLC is essential in guaranteeing the safety and efficiency of the entire process, facilitating accurate sequencing, and enhancing the overall reliability of the automated coconut shell charcoal powder production system. It is through this well-structured and logical control that the process operates smoothly, ensuring the safe and efficient production of charcoal powder from coconut shells.

Fig. 5.8 Ladder Logic Program

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

6.1 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the coconut shell charcoal powder machine offers a cost-effective solution for producing charcoal powder from coconut shells. This machine incorporates a range of mechanical components that efficiently convert coconut shells into fine charcoal powder. By utilizing a crusher, screener, and other associated systems, the machine effectively breaks down coconut shells and separates them into desired particle sizes. The compact design and affordability of this machine make it accessible to small-scale producers or businesses with limited budgets. The affordable coconut shell charcoal powder machine enables efficient processing of coconut shells, ensuring minimal wastage and maximum utilization of the raw material. It offers a sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional charcoal production methods, as it utilizes coconut shells, which are abundant and considered a waste product in many coconut-producing regions. Additionally, the machine's mechanical section, including the crusher unit, screening deck, conveyor system, and other components, work together to ensure smooth operation and reliable performance. Safety features are incorporated to protect operators and maintain a safe working environment.

Overall, the affordable coconut shell charcoal powder machine provides an economical solution for transforming coconut shells into high-quality charcoal powder. It opens opportunities for small businesses and entrepreneurs to enter the charcoal production industry, contributing to sustainable practices and economic growth.

6.2 FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope for coconut shell charcoal powder making machines is promising, as there are several potential advancements and opportunities for improvement. Manufacturers can focus on enhancing efficiency and productivity by optimizing machine design, streamlining processes, and incorporating advanced technologies like automation and machine learning algorithms. Energy efficiency and environmental sustainability will also be a priority, with the integration of energy-saving features and emission control technologies. Innovations in material sorting and processing, including advanced screening methods, can ensure the production of high-quality charcoal powder. Advancements in carbonization technology, such as pyrolysis and microwave-assisted carbonization, will further optimize the conversion of coconut shells. Additionally, the integration of waste management systems and market diversification into sectors like cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and energy storage offer exciting avenues for growth. Modular and scalable designs will enable businesses to adapt machines to their specific production needs, making coconut shell charcoal powder production a versatile and sustainable industry.

CHAPTER 7

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